

Average Energy and the Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation

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In a previous note, it was suggested $W(x,t)$, the time-dependent wavefunction, serves as a normalization function for conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$ and $P(E/t)$ and changes like $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ under $x \rightarrow x+b$ and $t \rightarrow t+a$ (a, b infinitesimal) except that p and E are replaced with conditional averages. In this note we first try to examine the physical implications of this and secondly, try to consider the meaning of average energy for the time-dependent Schrodinger case.

Transformation Properties of $W(x,t)$

In previous notes, it was suggested $W(x,t)$ serves as a normalization constant for conditional probabilities based on the idea that one has a particle which behaves in free space as $\exp(ipx - iEt)$. Here, this is understood to mean there are two channels each for probability in x and t i.e. $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ and $\exp(iEt) = \cos(Et) + i \sin(Et)$. The two pieces (for x and t independently) average separately. It is then argued that a potential $V(x,t)$ can cause transitions from one E to another and one p to another. Conditional probabilities are given by:

$$P(p/x) = f_p(t) \exp(ipx) / W(x,t) \quad \text{and} \quad P(E/t) = g(E,x) \exp(iEt) / W(x,t) \quad ((1))$$

$W(x,t)$ then has the property that it transforms like $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ under $x \rightarrow x+a$ and $t \rightarrow t+b$ except with p and E replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$ (obtained using ((1))).

The time-dependent Schrodinger equation immediately follows from equating $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$ with $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle + V(x,t)$.

For the sake of argument, however, one might suggest a different form of the conditional probability, say:

$$P(p/x) = f_p(t, x) \exp(ipx) / W(x,t) \quad ((1b))$$

This might be more in keeping with the idea that kinetic energy is high at some x points and low at others. This might be reflected in the weights $f_p(t,x)$. Thus, the idea that one use $f_p(t)$ instead of $f_p(t,x)$ must be based on physical consequences. It has been suggested that the choice of $f_p(t)$ leads to a $W(x,t)$ which transforms like $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ except with p and E replaced with conditional averages.

It seems one must consider the conditional probability in a different manner. Consider the classical case of an accelerating particle at x at t . It has a velocity and acceleration, but for $v=dx/dt$ one does not consider acceleration occurring in dx in the tiny time dt . Similarly, in the

quantum mechanical time-independent problem, one averages over $\exp(ipx)$ states in order to create a new averaged $\exp(i \langle p \rangle x)$ state, without regard to acceleration. $\langle p \rangle$ changes from one x point to another, so it as if there were acceleration which is not surprising because there is a $V(x)$. At x , however, one only wants the average $\exp(i \langle p \rangle x)$. Thus,

$$d/dx \exp(i \langle p \rangle x) = i \langle p \rangle \exp(i \langle p \rangle x) \quad \text{so}$$

$$i \langle p \rangle = d/dx \exp(i \langle p \rangle x) / \exp(i \langle p \rangle x) \quad ((1c))$$

Thus, the conditional probability approach must reflect this and ((1b)) is rejected. The conditional probability is based on examining ((1c)) which holds for $\langle p \rangle$. Once one has the conditional probabilities ((1)), one can apply them to any function of p . In particular, one can find $\langle p^2 \rangle / 2m$ conditional and equate this to $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$, the classical kinetic energy. This then gives the time independent Schrodinger equation.

It is not a coincidence that $W(x,t)$ transforms like $\exp(ipx - i Et)$ with p and x replaced with conditional averages. Quantum theory is based on the idea of such an averaged (although two channel averaged) object, it seems.

One may ask whether there are further consequences of such a choice. We argue, that the choice of $f(p,t)$ (and $g(E,x)$ not $g(E,x,t)$) leads to a theory which is dependent on spatial and time fluxes i.e. $d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ and $d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t)$. The spatial flux physically represents i times the conditional average of momentum at x and the time flux i times the conditional average of E . Furthermore, the spatial flux $u(x,t)$ and time flux $iE(x,t)$ are directly related to the classical force, which is the driver for changes in classical mechanics. In particular, consider taking d/dx (the partial of x) of:

$$-i d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t) = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t) + V(x,t) \quad ((2))$$

This leads to:

$$d/dx (-i E(x,t)) = - d/dt (i \langle p \rangle \text{ conditional}) = -1/2m (d/dx)^2 W(x,t) / W(x,t) + 1/2m [d/dx d/dx W(x,t)] / W(x,t) - F(x,t) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) contains the classical force $F(x,t)$, the spatial flux $u(x,t)$ and d/dx of the time flux or d/dt of the spatial flux. Thus, this looks like a Newton type equation for spatial flux $u(x,t)$ as discussed in (1). The point we wish to make is that the form of the conditional probability ((1)) leads to the transformation properties of $W(x,t)$ under changes of x and t , but these are directly related to spatial flux and time flux. Thus, the conditional probability definitions, in the form of ((1)), lead to a flux driven theory, although this is not apparent from simply examining the time-dependent Schrodinger equation which is energy based. Average spatial flux is a physical quantity directly

related to changes in spatial density etc. It should also be noted that the conditional averages performed use the idea of two probability channels, e.g. $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$, with the two averaging separately.

To see this perhaps in a different way, consider the time-independent situation:

$$\text{KE classical } (x) = E - V(x) = \left[\text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x)$$

If one transforms $x \rightarrow x+b$ the change of the LHS is:

$$d/dx (\text{KE classical}) = \text{Force}(x) = \left[\text{Sum over } p i p^3 f_p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) - \text{KE}(x) d/dx W(x)/W(x)$$

Thus, using f_p versus $f_p(x)$ has consequences in terms of dynamics.

As noted in a previous note, the RHS side of ((3)) represents $-1/2m \langle i p^3 \text{ conditional} \rangle - 1/2m \langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$.

One should not be overly concerned with the i appearing above as it combines with i in $\exp(ipx)$ if one has $f(p)=f(-p)$ symmetry.

Energy in the Time-Dependent Picture

For the time dependent case, one may write:

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } E \ g(E, x) \exp(iEt) \quad ((4))$$

This raises the question as to the meaning of E . For a time-independent situation, ((4)) should collapse to a single E with $g(E,x)$ representing $W(x)$. $W(x)$ may be written as a Fourier series $\text{Sum over } p \ f_p \exp(ipx)$ suggesting that all momenta are involved to produce a single E . Thus, the single E seems to be an average energy. $W(x)$ is a physical resonance state. In ((4)) one is summing over a continuum of such resonance states $g(E,x)$. Given that each $g(E,x)$ contains $\exp(ipx)$ with a weight, ((4)) could be rewritten as:

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } p \ f_p(t) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Here $f_p(t)$ includes the internal weight associated with $\exp(ipx)$ in each $g(E,x)$ together with $\exp(iEt)$, summed over all of the E 's. Thus, it seems that for the time dependent case, $E(t,x)$ is a conditional average (using the two channels $\cos(Et) + i \sin(Et)$) of all of the different E 's of the states $g(E,x)$. For the single E case (time-independent) $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle + V(x)$ was forced to equal E , but now, the average of $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle$ for all $g(E,x) + V(x,t)$ must equal the conditional average of all of the E 's.

In ((4)), it is suggested one has resonance states each with a weight $\exp(iEt)$. One does not, however, have to perform a Fourier expansion. It is possible that $W(x,t)$ might be a product of factors with one factor $W_n(y,t)$ with $y=x-b(t)$ (as an example) reducing the time-dependent Schrodinger equation into a time dependent one (with the help of the other factors). Such is the case for an oscillator with an extra $x f(t)$ potential. The “spatial” conditional averages are now calculated using y and the set of E 's in the new ((4)) i.e. $W(x,t) = \text{factors} \times \sum \text{over } E g(E,y) \exp(i E t)$ collapses to $W(x,t) = \text{factors} \times g(E,y) \exp(i E t)$ with $g(E,y) = W_n(y)$, the usual oscillator eigenfunction, but now in the variable y . It should be noted, however, that $W_n(y)$ are eigenfunctions of a different Hamiltonian than the original one, i.e. one changes from an oscillator plus $x f(t)$ to an oscillator only in y . Thus, this approach is really the product factor approach, where an overall resonance solution may contain another resonance within it. For example, the time-independent oscillator has solutions $H_n(qx)W_0(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state solution. Thus, $W_n(x)$, a resonance, contains the factor $W_0(x)$ which is another resonance.

Cycling

In a previous note, it was shown the time-independent Schrodinger equation could be written with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ described by Fourier series. This leads to:

$$-1/2m p^*p f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = E f_p \quad ((6))$$

The interesting point in ((6)) is that a single E value holds for all p equations. Thus, there seems to be a resonance with $1/E$ representing perhaps a cycling time (from $\exp(iEt)$) with the various f_k 's combining with V_j 's to create an f_p .

For the time dependent case, $V(x,t)$ can be written as a Fourier series in t . This leads to:

$$E g(E,x) = -1/2m d/dx d/dx g(E,x) + \sum_{j+k=E} V_j g(k,x) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, a similar cycling equation exists except for the fact that one does not have a unique E for all equations ((7)). Each equation in ((7)) has its own E value.

Discrete Time-Dependent States?

It should be noted that although ((4)) uses an infinite set of $g(E,x)$ “resonance states” to create $W(x,t)$, this does not mean there is only one $W(x,t)$ which satisfies the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. For example, for the oscillator with the added potential $x f(t)$, the time-dependent solution allows for states separated in energy by $\sqrt{k/m}$ just as in the time independent case.

$W(x,t) = \exp[i b(t) y] \exp[i c(t)] W_n(y)$ where $y=x - b(t)$ and $W_n(y)$ is the time-independent solution of the oscillator, but now with the variable y (which includes time). $W_n(y)$ is associated with discrete energy levels. Thus, oscillations (like phonons) could excite this time dependent solution. This problem has been discussed in terms of fluxes in (2). Thus, features of “hidden” resonances based on only part of the potential may exist and have physical consequences.

Conclusion

It seems $W(x,t)$ transforms under $x \rightarrow x+a$ and $t \rightarrow t+b$ like $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ with p and E replaced with conditional averages because one is actually considering separately at x and then at t , an average of either $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(iEt)$ free terms, thus creating an $\exp(i \text{Pave } x)$ or an $\exp(i \text{Eave } t)$. If one uses a conditional probability approach based on this idea, this is reflected in the normalization constant $1/W(x,t)$ which transforms in this manner. This holds even though there is a potential $V(x,t)$ at each x,t . It is similar to the case of calculating dx/dt for an accelerating particle. In the interval dx , one does not consider the acceleration in calculating velocity. The velocity will change in the next dt interval. Similarly, in quantum mechanics, there is a spatial flux = $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ at one x point and a different one at the next point. One may still use the average of free $\exp(ipx)$ or free $\exp(iEt)$ to calculate the average at an x or t point. It is also seen that even a single E (as in the time-independent case) is an average energy representing a system of all possible p values. For the full time dependent case, one averages over all E resonance systems i.e. $W(x,t) = \text{Sum on } E g(E,x) \exp(iEt)$

References

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2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Dependent Harmonic Oscillator with a Time Dependent Force and Flux Balance (preprint, zenodo, 2019)